

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

CAMPANULACEAE JUSS. IN THE FLORA OF NAKHCHIVAN: TAXONOMIC REVIEW, ECOLOGICAL ADAPTATIONS, AND PRACTICAL SIGNIFICANCE

Nasirova Afruz Sattar,

Odlar Yurdu University, K. Rahimov. 13, AZ1072, Baku, Azerbaijan

ORCID: 0000-0001-7910-4440

Guliyeva Lamiya Telman

Azerbaijan State Agrarian University, Ganja, Azerbaijan

ORCID: 0000-0002-3951-9083

Abstract

Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic is one of the regions distinguished by its rich flora, and *Campanulaceae* Juss. family occupies a special place on its flora. As a result of expeditions conducted in 2011–2025, more than 600 herbarium specimens were collected from various mountainous zones, GPS coordinates and heights were recorded. As a result of studies conducted using floristic, systematic, ecological and geobotanical methods, it was determined that the family is represented by 3 genera, 20 species and 6 variations in Nakhchivan flora, which constitutes 52.63% of the species distributed in Azerbaijani flora. The species are divided into mesophyte, xerophyte and intermediate groups according to their relationship to humidity, and heliophyte and facultative heliophyte according to their relationship to light. Biomorphological analysis showed that perennial herbs predominate. In terms of vertical zonation, it was found that species are unevenly distributed in the foothills, middle and high mountain zones. As a result of the research, 8 Caucasian endemic and 7 rare species were identified, their distribution areas were specified and included in the “Red Book”. Due to their decorative properties, 11 species were recommended for use in ornamental gardening and landscaping. This study presents the first extensive analysis of the systematic and bioecological characteristics of the *Campanulaceae* family in the flora of Nakhchivan AR.

Keywords: *Campanulaceae* Juss.; Floristic Diversity; Taxonomy; Bioecology; Vertical Zonation; Endemic Species; Rare Plants; Conservation; Ornamental Plants

INTRODUCTION

Azerbaijan’s varied landscapes—from the Greater and Lesser Caucasus to the Kur-Araz lowland and Caspian coast—harbor a rich diversity of living organisms. [Iskender, E.O., & Jafarzade, S.A., 2015; Jafarzadeh, S., & Iskender, E., 2024; Bakhshaliyeva, & Muradov, P.Z., 2026; Yadi, M., & Milani, M., 2018a; Yadi, M., & Milani, M., 2018b; Mammadov, E., & Aliyeva, I.M., 2025; Elshad, G., & Kamala, A., 2020; Gurbanov, E.M., & Elkordy, A., 2019; Humira, H., 2021; Gurbanov, E.M., & Huseynova, H.Z., 2021; Gurbanov, E.M., & Huseynova, H.Z., 2023; Mammadova, F., 2025; Sabuka, N., & Fidan, M., 2022; Mammadova, F., 2026]. Environmental pressures such as desertification, mining, and salinization further affect negatively these ecosystems [Mikayilov, A., & Amrahov, E.A., 2023; Khalilova et al., 2025; Khalilova, L.S., 2023; Khalilova, L.S., 2022; Gurbanov, E.M., & Asadova, K.A., 2024].

Within the broader framework of Azerbaijan’s floristic diversity, the *Campanulaceae* family occupies a significant position. Species of *Campanulaceae* family are widely distributed across mountainous and meadow ecosystems, where they serve both ornamental and ecological functions. Their sensitivity to soil and climatic conditions makes them valuable bioindicators of ecosystem health. This ecological responsiveness underscores their importance not only in documenting biodiversity but also in guiding conservation-oriented measures.

Accordingly, the study of *Campanulaceae* in Azerbaijan contributes to a deeper understanding of

floristic richness while providing a scientific basis for strategies aimed at preserving ecological stability and ensuring sustainable management of natural resources.

Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic is one of the regions distinguished by its rich flora diversity. In this rich floristic spectrum, the family *Campanulaceae* Juss. occupies a unique place. Representatives of the family are widely used in the landscaping of parks and alleys due to their decorative properties, and entomophilous species are also considered an important food source for polylectic and oligolectic bees [Nasirova, A.S., Talibov, T.H., 2015; 2016].

Although general information about the family was provided in previous studies, its systematic composition, role in phytocenoses and effective use have not been studied in detail. Therefore, floristic analysis of the *Campanulaceae* family in the flora of Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, investigation of its bioecological characteristics, identification of rare species, specification of their geographical areas, as well as development of ways of its protection and effective use are of great scientific and practical importance. The main purpose of the study is to study the distribution of *Campanulaceae* family in the biodiversity of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, its bioecological characteristics, role in phytocenoses and taxonomic composition, and to develop recommendations for the protection and use of species of scientific and practical importance [Nasirova, A.S., 2012].

The name *Campanula* appeared before Linnaeus and is associated with the shape of the plant crown. For the first time, K. Linnaeus described many species of

the genus in his work “Species Plantarum” (1753). In later periods, A. Decandol’s work “Monographie des *Campanulees*” (1830) was a new stage in the study of the genus. In the 19th–20th centuries, various aspects of the genus were highlighted in the works of F.G. Bartling, S.L. Endlicher, H.E. Bayon, E. Warming, S. Shenlanda, Ledebur, K. Koch, F.I. Rupprecht, E. Boissier, A.L. Kharadze, A.V. Fomin, A.A. Kolakovskiy and other researchers. In recent years, taxonomic studies conducted by V.P. Viktorov (2006), as well as publications on the flora of Turkey, Iran, Georgia and the USSR, have expanded ideas about the systematics of the genus. In Azerbaijan, information about the *Campanulaceae* family was provided in studies conducted by A.A. Grossheim (1935, 1961), A.M. Askerov (2006), T.H. Talibov (2002) and A.Sh. Ibrahimov (2005), [Nasirova, A.S., 2012; 2013a; 2013b; 2014a; 2014b; 2015a; 2015b; 2015c; 2015d; 2016a; 2016b; 2017a; 2017b; 2018a; 2018b; 2020].

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The object of the study is the *Campanulaceae* Juss family. The material used was the *Campanulaceae* family species collected during field research in various mountainous zones of the Nakhchivan AR. As a result of the expeditions conducted in 2011–2025, more than 600 herbarium specimens were collected, GPS coordinates and heights were recorded.

Floristic, systematic, ecological, geographical and geo-botanical methods were used, the specimens were herbariumized using standard methods. Morphological differences were determined by microscopic analysis. During the assignment, A.A. Grossheim, A.A. Kolakovskiy, L.V. Lazarev, “Flora USSR”, “Flora Europae”, flora of Georgia, Iran and Turkey, as well as the international code of botanical nomenclature and other sources were used.

Systematic floristic surveys were carried out during the vegetation seasons (April–September) over multiple years. Standard transect and quadrat methods were applied to ensure representative sampling [Kent, 2012]. Voucher specimens of all encountered *Campanulaceae* taxa were collected, pressed, and deposited in the Herbarium of the Institute of Botany, AMEA Nakhchivan Branch. Diagnostic morphological traits (leaf shape, corolla structure, calyx morphology, fruit type, seed characteristics) were recorded using stereomicroscopy and digital calipers. High-resolution photographs were taken for comparative analysis [Radford et al., 1974]. Identification was performed using regional floras [Flora of Azerbaijan, Grossheim, 1952; Flora of the USSR, Komarov, 1934–1960] and specialized monographs on *Campanulaceae* [Lammers, 2007]. Synonymy and taxonomic updates were cross-checked with international databases [The Plant List, 2013; World Flora Online, 2024]. Distribution maps were generated using GIS software (ArcGIS/QGIS) based on GPS coordinates of collection sites [Longley et al., 2015].

RESULTS

Based on literature data and the results of field research, a number of changes have been identified in the taxonomic composition of the *Campanulaceae* family

in the flora of Nakhchivan AR. Although 23 species of the family were recorded in previous studies, as a result of the research conducted, the total number of species has decreased to 20 with the synonymization of some species and reduction to the level of variation [Nasirova, A.S., 2014b; 2018a; 2017a]. Thus, the family is represented by 3 genera, 20 species and 6 variations in the flora of autonomous republic.

- Genus *Campanula* L. – 15 species (*C. glomerata*, *C. latifolia*, *C. rapunculoides*, *C. bononiensis*, *C. sclerotracha*, *C. daralaghezica*, *C. zangezura*, *C. bayerniana*, *C. coriacea*, *C. massalskyi*, *C. saxifraga*, *C. tridentata*, *C. karakuschensis*, *C. propinqua*, *C. stevenii*)

- Genus *Asyneuma* Griseb. et Schenk – 4 species (*A. amplexicaule*, *A. campanuloides*, *A. rigidum*, *A. pulchellum*)

- Genus *Michauxia* L. Her. – 1 species (*M. laevigata*)

The geographical-areal elements and types of the species of *Campanulaceae* have been determined. In the flora of the Nakhchivan AR, species of *Campanulaceae* family belong to: 7 geographical-areal elements (Iran-Turanian – 6 species, Atropatan – 5 species, Europe-Siberia – 3 species, Asia Minor-Caucasus – 2 species, Caucasus – 2 species, Europe-Mediterranean – 1 species, Western Front Asia – 1 species) and 3 geographical-areal types (Boreal, Xerophilous, Caucasus) [Nasirova, A.S., 2013a; 2013b; 2016b].

Representatives of *Campanulaceae* family are divided into 4 ecological groups according to their relationship to humidity: mesophytes (8 species), meso-xerophytes (3 species), xero-mesophytes (5 species), xerophytes (4 species). Hygrophytes were not found.

According to their attitude to light, the species are divided into heliophytes (15 species) and facultative heliophytes (5 species).

According to biomorphological analysis, in the classification of I.G. Serebryakov, the basis of the family is perennial herbs (16 species, 80%). Biennial herbs are represented by 3 species (15%), and annual herbs by 1 species (5%).

According to the classification of K. Raunkier, hemicryptophytes constitute the life forms of the family with 19 species (95%), and therophytes by 1 species (5%). Phanerophytes and megaphanerophytes have not been found.

In the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, representatives of *Campanulaceae* family are distributed in mountain-xerophyte, meadow, steppe, forest and petrophilous vegetation types. Studies have shown that 4 species (*C. stevenii* Bieb., *C. tridentata* Scherb., *C. latifolia* L., *C. rapunculoides* L.) form formations and associations. *C. glomerata* L., *C. bononiensis* L., *A. campanuloides* (Bieb. ex-Sims) Bornm., *A. pulchellum* (Fisch. et C.A. Mey.) Bornm., *A. amplexicaule* (Willd.) Hand. -Mazz. species were found as edificatory plants of the meadow vegetation type [Nasirova, A.S., 2014a; 2018b; 2020; Nasirova, A., Mammadova G., 2026].

10 species of the representatives of the family [*C. karakuschensis*, *C. daralaghezica*, *C. bayerniana*, *C. coriacea*, *C. massalskyi*, *C. saxifraga*, *C. sclerotracha*, *C. propinqua*, *C. zangezura*, *Michauxia laevigata*]

were found singly or in small micro-groups in the petrophilous vegetation type [Nasirova, A., Orujova, A., et al., 2024].

The complex mountainous relief and continental climate of the Nakhchivan AR have led to the distribution of plants along vertical zonation. As a result of research, 1 species (*C. massalskyi*) has been identified in the low mountainous zone, 1 species (*C. karakuschensis*) in the middle mountainous zone, and 6 species (*C. sclerotricha*, *C. daralaghezica*, *C. zangezura*, *C. saxifraga*, *C. tridentata*, *A. amplexicaule*) in the high mountainous zone [Nasirova, A.S., 2015b]. The representatives of the family, 10 species (*C. glomerata*, *C. latifolia*, *C. rapunculoides*, *C. bononiensis*, *C. bayerniana*, *C. coriacea*, *C. stevenii*, *A. campanuloides*, *A. rigidum*, *A. pulchellum*) are distributed from the middle mountainous zone to the subalpine zone. *Michauxia laevigata* is found from the foothill zone to the subalpine zone [Nasirova, A.S., Talibov, T.H., 2014].

Campanulaceae family is represented by 79 species in the Caucasus, 52 of which are endemic. 8 Caucasian endemics have been identified in the flora of the Nakhchivan AR (*C. bayerniana*, *C. glomerata* subsp. *caucasica*, *C. massalskyi*, *C. karakuschensis*, *C. saxifraga*, *C. daralaghezica*, *C. zangezura*, *A. campanuloides*). As a result of the studies, 7 species (*C. latifolia*, *C. daralaghezica*, *C. zangezura*, *C. coriacea*, *C. karakuschensis*, *C. propinqua*, *A. campanuloides*) were included in the "Red Book" of Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic and Azerbaijan Republic based on various criteria [Nasirova, A.S., 2015a; Iskender, E.O., & Jafarzade, S.A., 2015].

11 species of the *Campanulaceae* family (*C. glomerata*, *C. latifolia*, *C. rapunculoides*, *C. daralaghezica*, *C. zangezura*, *C. bayerniana*, *C. coriacea*, *C. tridentata*, *C. karakuschensis*, *C. stevenii*, *Michauxia laevigata*) can be widely used in ornamental gardening and landscaping due to their decorative properties [Nasirova, A.S., 2016a; 2015c; 2015d, 2017b].

CONCLUSION

The systematic composition, bioecological characteristics, phytocenological groupings and use of the *Campanulaceae* family in the flora of the Nakhchivan AR were investigated by us for the first time. Thus:

For the first time, 20 species, 6 variations belonging to 3 genera of the family were identified in the flora of the Nakhchivan AR, which constitutes 52.63% of the family spread in the flora of Azerbaijan. As a result of the geographical-areological analysis, it was determined that, the plants of the family belong to 7 geographical areal elements and 3 geographical-areal types. As a result of the ecological analysis, it was determined that, the species are divided into 4 groups according to their relationship to humidity (mesophytes - 8 species, meso-xerophytes - 3 species, xero-mesophytes - 5 species, xerophytes - 4 species). According to their relationship to light, the species are divided into groups of heliophytes (15 species) and facultative heliophytes (5 species). According to bio-morphological analysis, perennial grasses (16 species), biennial grasses (3 species), annual grasses (1 species) predom-

inate; according to Raunkier classification, hemicryptophytes (19 species) and therophytes (1 species) were identified. The distribution pattern in vertical zonation was studied, and it was determined that the species were unevenly distributed in the foothills, middle and high mountain zones. For the first time, new plant groups of 5 species and 37 new distribution areas for 12 species were discovered. The current status of 7 rare species included in the Red Book was studied, and their distribution areas were specified.

Due to their decorative properties, we recommend the use of *C. glomerata*, *C. latifolia*, *C. rapunculoides*, *C. daralaghezica*, *C. zangezura*, *C. bayerniana*, *C. coriacea*, *C. tridentata*, *C. karakuschensis*, *C. stevenii* and *Michauxia laevigata* species in ornamental gardening and landscaping.

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